

MEVLEVI MUSIC AND WHIRLING

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Spiritual traditions come and go on this planet. Some remain for many centuries even millennia. Others mutate or change with time. Sometimes it is the politicians or society leaders who change them or even ban their practise. One which I have been intimately connected with is the tradition of the Sufis known worldwide as the whirling dervishes. Also known as the Mevlevi, named after the great Sufi Saint known as Mevlana or Rumi, from whom it originated.

The tekkes (dervish lodges) and the tradition of Mevlana have been recognised by the World Heritage organisation called UNESCO. But this recognition came too late. By the time the world had woken up to the 700 year old tradition, it had been politically outlawed by Mustafa Kemal Ataturk during the cultural revolution which he instigated in Turkey, during the 1920's. Not only the Mevlevi but dozens of other Sufi orders were banned from continuation and their land and buildings were confiscated by the state. Several attempts were made to revive the tradition of Rumi on the grounds that the Mevlevi only brought benefit to the community. But finally the only way it has been allowed to continue is as a public or tourist attraction; or rather – spectacle I would say. This show is not truly Mevlevi. Information in this paper has not been told before.

The true tradition was not a public show, it was held in private Tekkes under the control of a holy man called the Sheikh. Many people will not know details of how the tradition was carried out. But as I said above, I have been intimately connected to this tradition, hence the interview made in 1995 which forms the main part of this paper may partly fill the gap in the ignorance of what the whirling ceremony and the music meant for the true Mevlevi dervishes 100 years ago. This paper may disappoint or surprise many.

A young man called Ralph was doing a degree course in Kings College, London, UK which he called, "**An Investigation into the Role and Significance of Music and Dance in religious movements.**" This title is not quite right in respect of the Mevlevi, as they were not a religious organisation. Also the word "**dance**" is not so relevant. But the text of the interview will explain these things. So read on. My comments in brackets. (---)

CONTENTS

Preliminary Questions	1	Is the Word Ecstatic Relevant ?	11
Personal Involvement	3	Who Else is Involved in the Ritual ?	13
What are Music and Dance in the Ceremony?	4	Epilogue	14
What are Sema, Zikr and Makam	5	Addendum - Corruption of Mevlevi Way	15
The Music in the Ceremony	6	History of the Sema told by a true Sheikh	16
Is There an Aim to Change the World ?	7	Overall Purpose of the Tradition	17
What about the Poetry?	8	More quotes from "The Music of Rumi"	18
Are the Instruments Significant ?	8	The Colet House London Connection.	18
The Significance of the Ceremony	9	Addendum by Cinuçen Tanrıkorur	19
Is There any Sense of Belonging ?	10	The prison of religion & tassavuf	20
		The Last Word Goes to Mevlana	21

[Supporting photographs on page 24](#)

Preliminary questions

A :- Let me first ask you about your personal position with regard to spiritual matters, what you believe and the reasons for this particular line of study. This is important because it will affect the way in which I answer your questions.

R :- I started this course partly because I find it a fascinating subject itself.

A :- Music or religion?

R :- Religion; I wanted to get away from (western) music, I was heavily involved in teaching children. My interest is twofold really, purely as it is something which is a fascinating subject across all religions.

A :- A broad subject not just Christianity?

R :- Precisely not, just Christianity; and also for my personal search for some kind of religiosity in my life as well. I wasn't expecting to get some kind of bolt of lightning. It just struck me that I would like to know more about it if I was ever going to have anything personal to do with it myself. So I have approached it from that direction. I think I have learnt a great deal.

A :- So you believe there is something (divine behind all religions).

R :- My personal belief is that I believe there is a transcendental order, something spiritual in our lives. I wouldn't go as far as calling it Christian or any other really. That's the whole point, the more I learn about these different things the more it seems to come together and yet keep further apart. A sort of unravelling, and before I get too ancient I might come to some conclusions, I haven't come to any yet.

A :- That's useful for me to know, because the sort of training that I've had in various things is that one has to be guarded about what is said. One of the fundamental principles of Sufism and Vedanta is that one doesn't disturb the mind of a person who doesn't believe or is not sure if they believe in God. They are in a certain state they are busy with their lives so they don't give it a thought, it is quite an important thing that one doesn't disturb that persons mind.

R :- You don't believe in evangelising.

A :- Not like the Christian idea of 'go around and try to convert everybody', that is something quite different, Sufism is almost opposite to that, so is Vedanta, they don't believe in proselytising or converting they haven't got any kind of mandate for that. Therefore we keep ourselves to ourselves, but if anybody shows an interest and they are obviously keen on that subject then there is more of an open aspect, otherwise one tends to be very guarded about these things. There are so many bad opinions about sects or groups that one has to keep away from the public eye.

R :- One thing I've learnt on this course is that the very word academic implies that it is not involved in any kind of judgmental aspect. That is the whole point. I've learnt more about how not to judge people, I've had to just purely make observations just gathering things for my own benefit.

A :- That is a very different aspect of it to be non-judgmental. An open mind is the best thing.

R :- I entirely agree that's my philosophy really not to pass judgement on anyone. I object because there are a lot of people I know who say (about new religious groups) that they are all like that (tarred with the same brush). I say look at the facts they aren't, that is totally unfair. I object quite strongly to the journalistic approach.

A :- To have a pre-conceived notion and then try to fit everything people say into that pre-conceived notion gives a distorted answer. It leads to distortion. What you are really

looking for is the true answer in a situation - the facts and the truth of that situation. -- That is good - we have a basis of where we are at. So now let us get on with the interview.

The Interview

Note :- *The interview was agreed to after a discussion about the reasons for his study. There was no warning of any questions, for that reason the answers may appear unprepared. What follows is a tape recording transcript. Ralph's questions are in **bold**. My comments in (---)*

Personal Involvement

R :- How long have you been involved with the Mevlevi order ?

A :- The Mevlevi, I've been involved in this since I was 32, so that is about 18 or 19 years. (since 1976)

R :- What is your role ?

A :- That has changed and evolved over the years but my contact with it was second, third hand at first. Like you hear about these things from second and third hand. But that has never been good enough for me I've always wanted to get first hand knowledge and experience direct from the horses mouth. So I started to go to Turkey after about two or three years, I didn't go straight away when I was first involved in it. I felt that there could be room for misunderstandings of the thing by those who were practising these things here (in this country, the UK), and I felt I had to go and find out directly and my suspicions were confirmed in a way over a period of time.

So I started to go to Turkey and meet the Mevlevi people there, and there are a few of them remaining and practising in their homes ([see page 23](#)), because it had been banned. There were also pseudo Mevlevi's doing it for show and it was never meant to be for show. I found out lots of things. My role at the beginning was like that but gradually, because of the confidence that developed between me and the leader over there, I felt my position was different.

So eventually I couldn't continue with the people in this country who were adapting or adopting the thing to suit their own culture. It was distorting it too much, or it was not quite to the point, I didn't think. From what I got by long and close association with the Mevlevi in Turkey, and I was going three times a year and sometimes staying a month at a time; and I learned the music. I was very attracted by the music which is a very central point of it.

I got to know them and they were calling me their brother or (the Sheikh was calling me) his son, you know they were calling me one of them. I felt that I absorbed from them something which I had never experienced in my life. Something very deep, something that was obviously very established and very strong. So eventually my role became changed. Sufi people don't always say directly what they expect. They give an inference as to what they hope or expect you to do. Like when I told them the sort of things we were doing at home as a family, because my children are interested as well. They said, "Your home is like a dervish lodge, a Tekke."

Things like that they say. I began to realise that my Sheikh who was getting older, and he had had an illness, was expecting me to come up with the goods, was expecting me to produce something. So we started a group in Sutton that's the reason why. We started something of our own and tried to get a few people interested to continue what we felt he was saying, was the real true way, as he wanted it to be continued. He knew it would die

out in his own country eventually but he was quite definite that it shouldn't die out altogether.

He wanted it to be continued in the proper traditional way and he spoke very specifically about certain things that you shouldn't do as well as what you should do. And I felt all these instructions he was giving me, gave me a responsibility. And my children were getting older and they were being given instructions by him as well and they were being taken into the family feeling over there. They were coming with me, they came many times and now they are in love with the feeling of the whole thing. (see page 23)

So it has become part of the family or the family has become part of it, you can't say which. And then we felt that, especially just before he died and he spoke very specifically, that he had given us a lifetimes job to do, to keep this thing preserved in the right way. It is a beautiful and pure thing which they had practised for hundreds of years. So my role has come to this point of being in this position; which I don't particularly want actually.

R :- You feel the responsibility of it all?

A :- I don't feel it's too heavy. I am happy to do it but if somebody else would take it from me I wouldn't be unhappy about that. But it would have to be someone that felt it in the same way as I do, I suppose.

R :- How often do you come together to perform?

A :- Well we play music every day, my daughter and I. My son is no longer living with us but he comes every week. We perform the whirling ceremony every week definitely, we don't miss. Unless there are too many of us away for some reason. We practise the ceremony music three times a week.

R :- So it's an integral part of your life?

A :- Oh yes, you have to. It is a whole-hearted thing. It has that effect on you, anyway it's very infectious.

What are Music and Dance in Relation to the Ritual ?

R :- Can you explain something of where it all comes from the origin of the music and the dance. If you can call it music and dance.

A :- I've done my own researches, it is very ancient it goes back even before Mevlana's time, he had revived something which had fallen into disuse or was corrupted at the time, the Mevlevi's that I spoke to were descendants of him (Mevlana) they were his great great great grandchildren as it were, their family tradition held lots of knowledge in it, and they said, "Yes the whirling did exist in a different form before." The form was changed the style was changed in His time. It is ancient very ancient.

R :- Are the terms 'music' and 'dance' appropriate, or do you think you could use other more religious terms?

A :- To use the term 'dance' could be misleading. It is more of a 'movement but it looks like a dance. It depends on your interpretation of the word 'dance'. If you can see that a person may dance for joy or have joy in the dancing but not for pleasure. Normal dance gives people a sense of pleasure. They exert themselves in a rhythmic way in a group and they get pleasure from it whether it is ballroom dancing or folk dancing or whatever, it's a pleasurable thing, but doesn't have a particular purpose.

This dance is a continuous whirling dance or whirling movement. The people trained in it have to fix their minds in a specific way and so you will not necessarily get pleasure,

in fact it can be quite painful and exhausting because your arms get very painful because you are holding your arms up. When you first get the training it can be very dizzying effect it has on you, but you overcome that very soon. But because of what it is, it is aiming at a particular transcendence within, to get a brief experience of something.

You see, scriptures talk about lots of things to do with religious experiences and people will imagine all sorts of things but they don't have those experiences; and it's in order to cut through the imagination, so that when you are talking about these things that you have had some glimpse of what it is. The whirling dance aims at ... it's not always successful it doesn't mean that just because you whirl you will get it, but there will be times when the group comes together in a certain magical feeling and you do transcend the feeling of being trapped in your body.

I can't explain it more than that; but you do have more of a conscious feeling of life around you. You can therefore understand the other subjects when they are being talked about in relation to actual experience. If I tried to describe the taste of an apple to you, and you had never eaten one you could imagine all sorts of things but if you have tasted one you would know what I was talking about.

So it's a movement which has got a purpose, a specific aim. So the whole ceremony, the music and dance builds up. It has a specific central aim a pointed feeling about it. It is sometimes successful in that sometimes not.

R :- What about the term 'music', would you say that is a fair way of describing it? I know that in Islam they don't like to use music at all.

A :- Most Muslims wouldn't accept that it is a Muslim thing at all. The centre of most Sufi orders has music and singing and dancing. They use music. Music in the normal worldly sense means we will sit down and attempt to make some harmonic sounds with instruments. The Mevlevi music (called Ayin) is not like that so you could find another word for it, I don't know.

It is the opposite of that, we sit down and empty ourselves without any real intention of doing anything. We hope that the music will play us. In other words the music exist it's eternal, and it is there. In some way it comes through us if we are good enough. We will have a go at it anyway. It's not like we are performers trying to do something. We are actually not trying to do something. We are trying to empty ourselves so the music will come more purely through us.

R :- So you don't see yourselves as a the source of the music?

A :- No, you see yourself only as a transmitting intermediary instrument. To communicate something that is always there to the people around.

What are Sema, Zikr and Makam ?

R :- Could you clarify the definition of three significant words for me? Sema, Zikhr and Makam.

A :- a) SEMA

Sema is a collective word meaning the whole business or point of the ceremony like that. There are many semas. Different dervish orders do a sema. It usually involves a group of people together, some musicians some singing of hymns or something; in a particular form that their own leader has given them, which is a kind of formula to generate some kind of higher state. It is the collective word used to describe all the activities surrounding the ceremony. You could say it is a dervish ritual.

b) ZIKHR

A rhythmic repetition. They use various words the sounds of which have quite deep meanings for them, there are so many of them. They get in a circle together and they repeat this. They start usually quite slow and very deep. There can be music in the background, maybe a flute or something to give them a feeling. It is not necessarily musical it is more of a chant. It is repeated over and over until the deeper meaning of it, or the feelings associated with it are reached.

They cut out all their thoughts of the world, their families and their jobs, they don't think about anything else. They are thinking about the meaning of that word and why they are together as a group. It can have a similar effect to a sema. We do that zikhr but not as long as other dervishes. Some just do zikhr all the time. We do short zikhr. We do one at the beginning which is musical and one at the end that is not.

R :- Would thou say it has a meditative effect?

A :- It is meditative. In the Roman Catholic church they say "Hail Mary" and they repeat that over and over with a rosary, and there are other things in Christian meditation, I think it's to centre the mind. A similar purpose. Most religions have got something like that. Muslims repeat Allah or some other word, I am not an expert on all these things.

c) MAKAM - A lot of musicians and musicologists have got this wrong. They think it is a musical mode. But you can write a full page description of a Makam, so it can't just be a musical scale, there is more to it than that. I wrote down at regular intervals when I was learning, my description of what I felt a Makam meant. I wanted to see how it changed for me. Gradually it expanded and it got deeper. I kept all these descriptions.

I think that the original term Makam means a 'path' but it is obviously also something to do with musical scales. One great musician said you could spend a lifetime studying one Makam only. It's like if you knew a person and you started to study their genealogy you'd study all their family connections but you would still be focusing on that person.

A Makam is a musical mode which is part of a family of modes and it has connections strong or weak to other modes. And it has a particular path; it has a particular set of intervals that are used and sometimes they are changed in a certain way. It is a very complex thing.

But to me it was a way which through music that you could connect with spiritual things because a Makam to me is like an angel. In the end my description of a Makam became a bit simpler. It was like a Divine Being which has manifested itself in our world in the form of music. In the end it came to that.

The Music in the Ceremony

R :- Could you explain how the music is constructed in the ayin or sema? I know it begins with Koranic recitations.

A :- We don't make any recitation from the Koran. We were told that as we are not Muslims we don't have to do that. It starts with a free rhythm improvisation on the flute [ney]. The ney is considered to be the divine representation, it is an empty thing, completely hollow.. That is done first but that is in the mode of the piece that is to follow. So you introduce the feeling or mood of that particular Makam.

When that has finished there is a set piece of music of fixed rhythm which is for procession. With the first drum beat the whirlers stand up. It is for the dervishes to process round the room. It has a nice steady beat to it. When that has finished there is

another improvisation on the flute, a short one. The dervishes take their (outer) robes off and start to whirl. The Makam returns with a fairly simple rhythm, seven or eight beats to the bar.

All the rhythms are repetitive, a bit zikhr like. The musical form fits the rhythm and is constrained within that rhythm. The composers will then move away from the Makam to other associated Makams. They may make radical changes and modulations and never come back, quite often they do come back to the base mode (of the ayin), they modulate away and come back. They are keeping it fairly low key. The second selam is definitely a change in rhythm, it is always one rhythm that is nine beats to the bar and it's slow. At this point the whirlers stop, they bow and they wait for permission to whirl again.

This is to make an abrupt change in the mood because the whirlers have come from their worldly state to the first stage in the progression within themselves. That development is arrested. The second selam is short it arrests and holds steady the development so far of the whole progress of the musicians the whirlers the whole thing. Then there is sometimes a short instrumental piece with no singing. The third selam begins with another rhythmic change. The third selam is the central part, the most important, because it builds itself up. It has three rhythms within it. It builds itself up to a crescendo type feeling with the meaning of the poetry and the tessitura or level of the music rises to a crescendo. So the climax of the whole thing is in the third selam.

As soon as it has passed that point it starts to come down. Then an abrupt change again, the fourth selam, to hold steady that development. To keep the person in that state because they are going to have to be introduced to the world of living here and now. In the fourth selam there is some fast processing music. It is not as fast as it was in the third but it can still be quite energetic, the energy levels have lifted by that time. Then there is finally another improvisation on the flute to gradually bring the thoughts and minds of the persons descending down. The flute begins high (pitch) and it comes down and down very slowly and finishes in a restful way.

You know then it has come to a complete conclusion and the dervishes bow and stay on the floor. They are then supposed to retain a sense of what they may have experienced, and take that into the world with them, into their ordinary life with them. As best as they can, you can't say what is going to happen. Sometimes the next day you will completely forget it.

Is There an Aim to Change the World?

R :- Is the aim to change the world around them?

A :- It is integral. It is to change a state of mind really, isn't it?

R :- And through that change to change society, you say take that into the world with them?

A :- I think it does have that effect. If (there are) a lot of good people in the world, people with good thoughts and so on, (it) is going to benefit the world, then that would be a side effect. That will happen. You don't have to make that happen.

The view is, the presence of good people is enough. The example spreads like an infection. I think they know that that may happen but it is not a direct aim. The main aim is to improve the consciousness and the life of the individual person.

What About the Poetry ?

R :- Can I ask you about the poetry? What is the link between the poetry and the music?

A :- The poetry is fixed for each particular piece of music. The music is put together by those people who were themselves whirlers or dervishes and they have got this inspiration. They feel so much for the poetry and for the purpose of the thing, they have become an instrument for a piece of music, it has come through them I think.

If you read descriptions of Mozart and the way he said he composed music he said it came out of the sky, he was only an intermediary. It came through him, it wasn't anything to do with him and a lot of the dervishes, if they were to explain, but they wouldn't, they would probably say the same. The music came through them, it is very inspired. The meanings in the poetry infect the music. Some of the meanings which are particularly strong cause very nice modulations in the music.

R :- Does the music follow even programmatically, the progress of the poetry?

A :- They are intimately connected, the music and the poetry. There is no doubt about that.

Are the Instruments Significant ?

R :- Is there symbolic significance behind the instruments?

A :- Definitely. The ney is the only musical instrument, the only one which carries the melody which we are told to use. In the last century a lot of Western influence came into the various dervish groups, and they started playing Western instruments in it. My Sheikh said that it was not acceptable. For the people who stuck to the true path that was not acceptable to expand it and turn it into an orchestral thing. It was meant to be a simple ritual music.

The main and original instruments are the flute, the drums and the cymbals. There is a stringed instrument called the rebab or rebek, which is also possible to use it has the sound of the human voice. The ney also should sound like the human voice. The rebab should never drown out the sound of the ney, it should always be less than the ney, because the first verses of Mevlana's Mathnavi extol the virtues of the ney.

R :- So what is special about the ney, can you explain that or not?

A :- They say that the human being is represented by the ney. There are seven holes cut into the ney (i.e. nine openings) and there are seven (nine) orifices in the human body, through which influences pass in and out of the human body. In that way it represents the human body. Also the ney begins its life in a reed bed. All the sections within a reed are separate from each other, there is a membrane that passes between them.

In order to make it into a ney these membranes are removed. So it becomes a complete empty pipe. This process also can happen to a human being. All the separate parts of your thinking, your psychology and the intervening membranes are removed. In other words you become a more unified person. Also the fact that the ney has not got anything in it. It is empty.

That emptiness is one of the most important Sufi things. To be egoless, to have less desires. What did Jesus say "Sell all that you have and follow Me". It is the same idea. It means all this idea of 'me and mine'; possessions, selfishness and so on, anger etc. All these things are removed and when they're removed you're empty. Now the ney plays

music because it is empty. If it ever had anything in it, it wouldn't play. In the same way the symbolism is that. It is quite nice I think.

The Significance of the Ceremony

R :- Can you expand on the significance of the glimpse which you get in the dance?

A :- It has to be experienced I would say really, to understand what it means. In a way, every time you take part in it you have to overcome certain things in yourself. (to explain something which can be related to by the questioner) Like a gyroscope for instance, because it is whirling round two things one inside the other, you can't easily change the direction of it. If you've ever spun a bicycle wheel and held it by the axle, free from the bicycle, if it is really spinning fast and you try to change the direction of it you can't do it.

It is as if there is a mystical force holding that bicycle wheel from being turned, because it is spinning in a certain direction you can't easily change the direction. It is Newton's laws of motion actually. In a strange way that is what happens with the whirling, the fact that you are continuously going around in a certain way. What looks from the outside to be a bit chaotic, maybe the experience is one of steadiness. Making the character of a person with greater equanimity.

You are not moved or affected by the ups and downs of life. That is not to say you wouldn't do what you had to do practically but inwardly you would not be affected. You gain a steadiness. My understanding of all the religious things is you can't progress down a religious path unless you've got this steadiness, faith they call it in the Christian terminology. From that basis of steadiness you can go forward to understand other things. Something which helps this steadiness, yogis use meditation and things to find the same steadiness.

The steadiness itself is a platform for further progress, into things which most people would never ever believe they existed or understand descriptions of them, because their unsteadiness means they are too concerned with the events of their life. I think that is one of the fairly obvious benefits, there are many others, but that is one of the things you could relate to. (since you have not whirled).

R :- The aspect of Sufism relating to inward and outward, is the sema a way of turning in on yourself?

A :- Its more a way of finding - Jesus used this term "rock", building on rock instead of sand, why did he say sand? If you think of your own experience as a child certain things that happen to you, you view them in a certain way (at that time) later when you get older you view them differently. The thing itself is the same, your view is different.

Depending on the circumstances of your life the same thing can be viewed so many different ways. Because the basis upon which you view things is always changing there is no stability. This gives people a lack of stability in their lives. The 'outer' is always apparently confusing and difficult to understand for people because they are inwardly unstable.

Building on the sand, if they had dug deeper the rock was there, Jesus didn't explain that because it was obvious to anybody, sand came from rock anyway, so if you get rid of the instability by taking it away you would find that underneath peoples stability is there. If you therefore find that, as a basis for seeing the world on the outside, you will find that

you are not confused with changing and conflicting views of the outside. It means you get more constancy in your view.

R :- And the music and dance is a way of reinforcing that?

A :- Yes. The inner and outer is a quite an important concept. I'd like you to understand the 'inner' and the 'outer' in that way. The 'outer' is what it is. If you find something better on the 'inner' you can relate to the 'outer' in a more constant way.

R :- Is the music and dance a way of guiding people down the mystical path?

A :- When you talk of a mystical path then I would say that nothing leads you to that at all. I can only quote, there was a story about St. Francis of Assisi. He became a saint, there is no doubt about it, he found Absolute Reality in his life. He was a beautiful man, a wonderful man. In the early part of his life he was seeking and he found this old man who was blind from crying. He asked him about ultimate reality, about the mystical path. If there is a path or route, show me the way, the old man said, "There is no path there is only the abyss and you must jump across it. All paths are nothing; they are all on the earth."

R :- Cannot then rituals of music and dance give you a taste or glimpse of the mystical path?

A :- Tastes are possible but only I would say through the 'Grace of God'. In other words if you were in a correct condition, if it was beneficial to you at the time, the 'Grace of God' gives you a taste. You can't get it by anything that you do, you may do all the right things but if God didn't give you that Grace or that insight at the time you won't get it. So it's not dependant on humans. This is where the human being is finished, it's over to Him.

So the dance, the music, the meditation, any of these things are preparation only. Then (with that understanding) there is no path, you depend upon something else. That is a lot to do with whom you have connections as well. If you have had connections with a saint a holy person (realise soul) that can help a lot with that abyss, the gap between (the worldly life and the spiritual life). It is something for which words fail in the end. Yes, words do fail there.

Is There any Sense of Belonging ?

R :- Does the music and dance ritual (ayin) bring a sense of belonging to individuals? Does it bring people together? You mentioned for instance the sense of responsibility for continuing the tradition.

A :- Ah yes, right. That certainly is an effect that a lot of these things have on people. An ordinary thing like belonging to the boy scouts would make you feel like that. It's the experience of sharing things; there is that aspect to it. But these are sometimes temporary feelings, the temporary feeling of belonging to a club or group. That can happen with ordinary worldly things.

There is something more special than that in a way. There is one element in all humans and creatures that is the same in all. When you have stripped away all the differences of character, personality and so on. When I say stripped away I don't mean you have done away with them and say they are useless, because they are not. Character and personality are very important and necessary things to have. What you've done is, you've seen that they are only the covers of something underneath.

You know that you have characters in a Punch and Judy show that pop up and down. They have the same hand inside moving them all, and yet they look so different on the outside. And they are all going through a play; those puppets are performing a thing which has to be done. And our lives are like that, as Shakespeare said "All the world is a stage and we are all ---" he said the same thing. He was a great man he was a mystic character. If you read what he says, he says a lot of truth.

So you find that hand, or that oneness. You find that which is not the same as sharing activities like the boy scouts. It is something that when it is between yourself and other people, those people become, without words but they do become very special to you. You don't find it with others so easily. When you are together with those people you find that thing, which leads to this sort of happiness state, it's not happiness because it has not got an opposite.

We think happiness and sadness. My teacher in India He says, "There is in the world good and bad, happiness and sadness, opposite sides. Duality everywhere." But he says "When you come to joy, it is joy (on one side) and the other side is joy. It's all joy." It's because you find that and you experience it and you know its real, and you can't be talked out of it by anybody else, because you know that they (maybe) haven't experienced it (yet).

Is the Word Ecstatic Relevant ?

R :- Do you think the word 'ecstatic' is a fair word to use when describing the state of the dancers and musicians?

A :- No. I think it can be misleading. The word ecstatic relates to a chemical feeling in the body. Sometimes people get a flood of adrenaline a flood of some chemistry or something and they feel a chemical high, which they think is something happening to them. But it is only chemistry flowing around the senses, the nervous system, the brain and so on. But it goes. As soon as the chemistry is gone it goes. That is a possible interpretation of the word ecstatic that would be very misleading.

(in the past) I think the term ecstatic has been used by people at a time when it had a deeper significance to it. People who travelled to Turkey and wrote about things that they had seen and shared in feeling of it. But it's not a physio-chemical biological thing. It is as if there is something behind the mind which is very bright. Like you may have a cloudy, stormy day but you know the sun is out there bright and shining as it ever was. You don't forget that.

That brightness never goes. Even in the middle of the night the sun is there shining away, just because you are round the other side of the planet (it doesn't stop). That thing which never goes, never dies, is not a temporary thing. Ecstasy in this modern world is something that comes and goes. But this kind of state is something you discover that it was always there and always will be. Even if you know you might not always be aware of it, because of your (forgetfulness).

R :- Would you use the term 'spiritual' to describe your experience?

A :- What does it mean? We have to define the term, don't we? The word spiritual can mean so many different things. (for example) Somebody in a fortune tellers tent, it is all these ideas of predicting the future and so on. Spiritual healing you hear about. But to a person who has studied the things that I have studied and who has had the close contact with people who don't think theories, they don't think text book ideas. They know. They could write all the text books themselves if they wanted to.

They are people who have really experienced. To that kind of person spirit is the thing that everything has become. Things have become what they are because of spirit. For example so many things happen from electricity; you get whirling movements, you get heat, you get light, you get magnetism. You get so many things but the thing it comes from is one thing. Even in this world they don't fully understand it, even though they can generate it.

There is one thing which is the cause of all the things that exist, although those things are very different in their appearances. That is spirit. And therefore everything is spirit, there is no difference between spirit and the world, to some people. Although you know your sense organs are programmed and geared to contact the physical world. And they will mislead you to think there is variation and variety.

We have these words 'insight' , in + sight and 'intuition' in our own language and it means there is something within you, inside you that knows otherwise. Here is an example: you see the sun going from east to west but you know that it doesn't go from east to west because if you're educated you know that the sun stays where it is and the earth turns, but, you can't deny your senses. All your logic will look at it and will say the sun is rising and setting. But because of something you've come to understand through education you know the sun doesn't move from East to West, it never moves from East to West.

That is a knowledge you have that is contrary to experience. That's the example I mean. This knowledge of spirit is like that. You know it because of what you have studied and because of what you have experienced. Your actual experience of the world you know is contrary to the truth of the situation.

R :- So you see spirit as an underlying continuous transcendence which passes through everything.

A :- Yes everything is spirit, but the senses don't show that.

R :- Would it be right to say that the Mevlevi Ayin is a way of opening a window on that?

A :- Yes it does. You know the story of Alice in Wonderland? It is brilliant, he was a priest you know (the author). What had she to do to get through the little window to the (beautiful) garden? She had to become small. That is the thing. That is the humility that is the egolessness. She did something in order to become less ego and personality and so on. That doesn't mean you have to give it up. I've still got character and personality and ego.

I will still say something in a certain way whilst others will say it another way, it doesn't mean you give all that up. You use it instead of it using you, that's the difference. Most peoples characters and personalities are manipulating them and using them, they are trapped in the prison of it. When you turn it on its head, you see it as a very valuable tool your character and personality become something which is a (useful tool) your not frightened of it. You can use it. But you are small, and by being small you get through that little window to the magic garden. That is a beautiful description in Alice in wonderland.

R :- Would you say transformed by the ritual?

A :- I would say my life has become completely turned on its head, it has been transformed. I am a happy joyful person, I never get moods, never sad. And I love everybody, I don't have any friends or enemies or whatever, all people are equal to me. I

would never have thought as a young man that I could have become like that. I was very much here and there and opposite (to this equanimity).

R :- Would you say you are transformed in the ritual itself?

A :- I think that happens to some extent. The person who gets accepted to be trained for the ritual will have gone far enough already to be ready for that kind of experience which would come. That's where I say preparation is important, a person has to be of a certain sympathy towards the thing.

You wouldn't take someone off the street and teach them to whirl it would devastate their lives. It would be not helpful to them. You wouldn't want to do that. The purpose is not to do that, to upset peoples lives. It is to bring about a different thing, and that person has really got to want it. First some contact with it and then they have to want it more and more.

Two of my children learned to whirl they really wanted to. The youngest is now twenty she has not yet learned to whirl. Maybe she will one day. They have never been coerced into doing it. No one said you must do it. It has to be that the person feels in themselves that they want to. The other two did want to there was no doubt about it. We weren't sure whether they should. We went to Istanbul and we asked the Sheikh, "What do you think". He said, "Yes, if they want to they must, I did when I was young." He said "As long as they are over seven or eight years of age then they are thinking for themselves."

Who Else is Involved in the Ritual

R :- So are you the only ones in England that are doing this?

A :- No, there are others, another group I know who are very secretive, they are the ones who I learned with at first. One of the differences is that they do not use live music. We always use an element of live music and sometimes completely live music. The Sheikh in Istanbul insisted on live music. It is so important to have that live element.

R :- Is it because it changes it every time you do it?

A :- Yes its different always different, never are two times the same. Also the music infects the whirling the whirling inspires the musicians. The musicians become better at the music because of the feeling they are getting, this is not necessarily technically better, it is becoming better intermediaries to convey the music the feeling of the music through you. It all helps itself, if you only have a tape recording you can't inspire a tape recorder whatever you do, it will just blab out the same thing. So I understood what he (the Sheikh) meant, and we are trying to do what he wished.

R :- Why do you feel it is so important to keep this tradition authentic?

A :- Its not so much just the physical things that you do. There are some things which physically we haven't done because they are not appropriate, and I know my Sheikh would not bother about that. It is certain (causal) things, if you ever did chemistry and you want to get a certain compound at the end, and you have to add this and add that in a certain order. Maybe it is a long lengthy process, you have to distil this, separate this etc. so many things and the process over a period of time has been sorted out and found to be more or less the only way you will get that compound.

If you change one element somewhere you might get a different compound but you wont get the one you are going for. You might be lucky if you can switch the process back in the middle. Once someone has set up a process you would tend to stick to that

wouldn't you? That process if it was in the scientific sense. As long as the main elements the main thing is right, you can't be guaranteed, that we know every time we go to the sema.

We don't go with any expectations. We just do what we have been told in principle is the same thing, with the same thoughts in our minds, what has been done for centuries which can't be changed. Minor details maybe, but in principle the formula which they had derived which will reach that goal. At first you do it because of faith in that, later you do it because of experience. Firstly you stick to the traditional method because you don't know anything else, and if you tried something else you might fail, also because of your feeling of allegiance to those who taught you.

After a while the reason (for doing it traditionally) changes, the reason why you stick to the main elements of the process is because you know it leads to the goal, and you wouldn't want to do anything which meant that the goal was missing. If you want to get to Oxford Circus you can get a No. 12 bus from somewhere, it will take you there, and there are so many buses that will take you to that point, that's why I say there are so many religions.

But it is the point they come to that matters, not the route. But if you are part way on the journey and you think "I will get this other bus." and it goes off at a tangent, then you don't get what you are aiming for. It is the aim that is important not the vehicle that carries you there. That's the main thing I would say about that. (keeping to the traditional way). The vehicle isn't so important, the destination is important. The vehicle is only important if it is going your way. So don't switch vehicles unless your sure the one your switching to is going the same way.

(for more information go to - <http://www.livingtraditions.tilda.ws/alan>

END OF INTERVIEW

Epilogue

This interview was nearly thirty years ago (in 2024). I still visit friends in Konya, Turkey twice every year. So I can say the public show of the Mevlevi ritual is unchanged over these decades. As far as what is happening in the UK I cannot say with full certainty. But before the middle of this century it may be that Kemal Ataturk will have achieved his goal; and the true Mevlevi way will become history. There are many groups in the USA and around the world who make a ritual similar to the Turkish show. My family played a Mevlevi Ayin for one such group when they were visiting London UK, some decades ago. I was not impressed by their approach to the subject. Hear my family playing Ayins at :-

<https://www.youtube.com/@dr.alanwenham-prosser/videos>

As far as I know there never was a true Mevlevi Sheikh who saw that the USA, or western style countries were a suitable place for the true Mevlevi ceremony to be continued. Many would probably not agree with me. But in the vacuum created by the absence of the living Tekkes in Turkey, many people saw the prestige to their character could be improved by adopting the title Sheikh. Much like the situation in India, where there are hundreds of false holy men to every truly enlightened person.

My daughter and I are still working on correct notation of all the Mevlevi Ayins. We hope to finish that several decades long project within the next year or so.

I hope this paper has been of value to some readers. Please ask me any questions if you need clarification on any point. Email alan.prosser@btinternet.com

ADDENDUM

What depths will they go to destroy the tradition of Mevlana

These pictures are of a whirling ceremony in the street of Konya in front of the conical dome which is above Mevlana's tomb – made on 21st September 2025. It was in front of a large crowd of Turkish people who are most likely uninformed of what the true ceremony should be. This is how far away the ceremony has travelled from its origins. Read on.

The Corruption of the Mevlevi Way

Here follows an extract from the book , “The Music of Rumi” which clarifies some of the above points raised in the interview:-

QUOTE - from chapter 7

There is one important issue which I should raise here in respect of the Mevlevi way. It is to do with the representations of the Whirling Ceremony which have been seen around the world since the 1950s. These began after the Turkish government relaxed the legal ban on the Mevlevi and their ceremony. The original relaxation only applied once a year to the special day of the Mevlevi on 17th December. This is the anniversary of the passing of Rumi from this world, which in 1953, was allowed to be celebrated in Konya for the first time since 1925. In the first few years of the relaxation those who gathered in Konya were the dervishes who previously had connections with the closed Tekkes or were their descendants. They were the true Mevlevi. They had all been continuing the ceremony in their private homes in defiance of the legal ban. Resuhi Baykara, the man who instructed me for many years, was the Sheikh at that time.

As time passed the Konya Tourist Association took an interest in the ceremony and eventually the press and other public media were involved. There is a documented incident in 1967 when Resuhi forbade a photographer to violate the Sema space,¹ which is reserved for the feet of dervishes during the ceremony. After that Resuhi did not continue in Konya due to the ceremony becoming more of a tourist attraction.

The changes that occurred in the years to come in the Konya ceremony have gradually made the whole event into a touristic show. The governments of Turkey and Konya have controlled the event and have even taken over the appointment of musicians and the whirlers, who are not necessarily connected with the Mevlevi. Turks whom I have known in Konya have been allowed to take part in the event for up to three years; after which the whole company may be changed. This is an attempt to prevent it becoming a dervish activity. The Turkish government have promoted it as a cultural event and it has been allowed to travel to many countries world-wide as a show.

The truth of this event now is that it is far from being a Sufi ceremony any more than a Russian ballet performance is. Even so it does give rise to a certain sense of awe in those who do not really know what it is they are watching.

END OF QUOTE FROM BOOK

¹ See - Friedlander I. - (New York 1975).

History of Sema told by a true Sheikh

I should add to the above, that the demise of the Mevlevi ceremony began much earlier than Ataturk's time. When I asked Resuhi Baykara (the last real Sheikh from the Yenikapı Tekke - and also my Sheikh and guide in all things Mevlevi) what did he think about the closing of the Mevlevi Tekkes? Was it a wrong thing to do? His answer was:- "No it was the best thing that happened." This really surprised me as I always thought that it was a sad thing that Ataturk did. Hence I needed an explanation of this statement. He told me that near the end of the 19th century (CE), the corruption of the Mevlevi Tekkes had already started. Some Tekkes had introduced Islamic prayers and the recitation of the Koran. Also screens were introduced to separate women during the Sema. And women were losing their equality of the old tradition. (there had been female Sheikhs in the past). The ceremony was slowly becoming a religious event, which it never was before. If it had continued after Ataturk's time then by now (1980) it may have become unrecognisable to the true Mevlevi, Mevlana's family. Who had kept His tradition pure for about 700 years.

This I understood was a big change and a corruption. Tasavvuf (mysticism) is not like religion, which is for the population at large, for millions of people. Tasavvuf is not a religion. Mysticism is for those few who have sought escape from the prison of religion and have entered, or who seek to enter, the realm which is above all religions. It is not, like religion, for the population at large, although they may benefit from its presence in the community. This higher realm is the one which is the origin of all religions and all mystical paths, which lead to the love of the one Creator of us all.

Mevlana says in His **Mathnavi book 3; verse 4514 to 4517** :- my comments in (--).

"To be nigh (unto God) is not to go up or down (live in the world of opposites); to be nigh unto God is to escape from the prison of existence. (into non-existence). What room hath non-existence for "up" and "down"? Non-existence hath no "soon" or "far" or "late." (the mental world of opposite qualities). The laboratory and treasure of God is in non-existence. Thou art deluded (in your thinking) by existence: How should'st thou know what non-existence is?" (non-existence is eternal indescribable tranquility.)

Mevlana had escaped in this way. Hence he was truly qualified to say, "Come, come whoever you are ----". An invitation to all of humanity, regardless of ethnic origin or religious belief. Even including those with no recognised religion (i.e. the fire worshippers). But the demise of the Tekkes was already on the cards of fortune.

In the oldest recorded philosophy on this planet (Vedanta) in the Paingala Upanishad, Chapter IV verse 2, it is written that whoever reaches the highest goal (escapes from the prison) then 21 generations of that person will also have the chance to escape. This is the same number of generations of the last of the true Mevlevi when the Tekkes were closed. So Resuhi's acceptance of the closure of the Tekkes was a recognition of this ancient statement of the highest wisdom of mankind. It cannot be exceeded according to Vedanta.

But don't take away from this that 'family' tradition is some kind of free ticket to freedom from the prison of religion and human life. This can only ever happen with sufficient self-effort, whatever the status of your father or grandfather. Three things are necessary for escape from the prison. (1) True and correct teaching in written scripture, by those who have escaped. (2) True and correct guidance from living teachers who have themselves escaped. (3) Self-effort of the right kind guided by the first two on the list. These three are needed in combination.

The first two are beautifully provided by the Mevlevi family tradition. The third one is available due to the souls of those born again and again into the same family (i.e. reincarnation - remember Mevlana said :- "I died from being a mineral and was born as a plant. I died as a plant and was born as an animal - etc. etc. - - when was I less by dying."). No human soul ever dies, it is only reborn again to continue the journey, as

Mevlana indicated. And if we have made the right self-effort then we will not be less by dying. Making sufficient self-effort in each birth; in each family reunion, would eventually give sufficient merit to attain freedom from the prison.

See quote on "levels of being" page 20 below which is about levels of consciousness.

The family tradition of Mevlana provided all that was needed for such emancipation. And this family tradition complied with the most ancient wisdom of mankind, in terms of the number of generations. This is the wise way to understand this subject. Also do not limit the idea of 'family' to blood relations alone. Sometimes a non-blood related disciple will show to be more worthy than a blood relation. To such a worthy person the true Sheikh will say, "You are my son." or "You are my daughter." Such a relationship can be closer than ties of blood and genetics; since it exists in the non-changing world of spirit.

Overall Purpose of the Tradition as Passed on Through the Tradition

Mevlana spoke His epic work the Mathnavi, while whirling. His faithful follower wrote it down. They both worked on corrections after each session.

How is this relevant? Mevlana is a liberated soul, which means His inner being has become one with the Creator of the Universe. His consciousness is one with all aspects of the Creation. Knowing Him truly is to share in His consciousness and oneself become an inner unified being. This is the only purpose of the Sema ritual. It does not require a large show in front of many people. It is to return to that state of Mevlana during his recitation. Absorbed into union with the Creator through love of Him.

A true Sema is one musician to provide the divine melody, one semazen to emulate Mevlana when He spoke the Mathnavi. And one singer to sing the words of Mevlana with that divine melody. These three should aim to empty themselves of all personal limited psychology and to focus on that unified consciousness which can be experienced when standing before Mevlana's tomb in Konya, if the mind is empty.

Added to the above, from my experience; each of the three main elements (music, poetry, whirling) have the potential to lead the human consciousness to experience that oneness with the Creator. I say potential because they must be divinely inspired. The true music of the Sema, the Mevlevi Ayin, based on Pythagorean principles, is such a music. The poetry of a divine person such as Mevlana is, can provide that inspiration. The whirling movement made in response to the love arising from mental focus on love of the Creator, is such a movement. Each of these elements alone can lead human consciousness to oneness. When all three are together correctly inspired, there is no other known formula (as far as I know) which will lead the human experience to know the truth of human life.

That sense of inner stillness and unified consciousness present at Mevlana's tomb in Konya (and at the tomb of Shems of Tabriz in Konya) is what will eliminate the false sense of separateness from Him and bring us closer to the knowledge of who we really are. Not this limited mortal frame and separate ego. You will stand at His door and say, in answer to, "Who is there?" "It is thou." **See Mathnavi Book 1 - vv 3056 to 3063 et. seq..**

This was the real reason for continuing the Sema all those hundreds of years ago. Consider how far away the modern approach to the Sema has moved to become a touristic show; or any other kind of large group ; which does not observe these simple principles.

All those who join in things called Sema in this present century are far from being aware of this simple three person (and three element) Sema; which was passed to me by the last of the true Mevlevi in Istanbul during the 1980s. This true Sema has now almost passed into history, simply because the holiness which requires the above experience, is that which was handed down by those who received it by tradition. If those who stand as Sheikh or Çelebi do not carry this holiness (did not receive it) then they cannot conduct a true Sema however much they make imitations and dress up to look like dervishes.

MORE QUOTES FROM "THE MUSIC OF RUMI" BOOK

From the Preface

Rumi was a Persian Sufi. The Sufis of northern Persia and Afghanistan combined the philosophy of the Greeks and the Indians to form their way of life, based on a harmonious blending of knowledge and devotion. Hence I prefer to use the term "Pythagorean Sufi", where relevant, to avoid any confusion associated with the 20th century use of the word Sufi. Rumi's music, or Mevlevi music, is full of mystery and provides a means of deep communication for our inner being. In this respect it has been called food for the human Soul. My experience has shown that for it to carry out this function it needs certain "essential nutrients" in the form of naturally occurring intervals and microtones.

From the General Introduction

In my understanding there are seven elements which depict the Pythagorean spiritual approach :-

1. Knowledge of the Soul's identity with the Divine aspect of creation.
2. No association with a particular religion, but accepting members who follow any belief system or none.
3. Men and women are treated equally in every respect, since the Soul of Man has no gender.
4. The use of melody which is divinely inspired, sometimes combined with dance, as a part of the method to discover the True Self.
5. The harmonious blending of knowledge and devotion in the way the path is practiced.
6. Knowledge of the Soul's reincarnation on its continued journey.
7. Leading a regulated, systematic and disciplined life, including truthfulness, tolerance, compassion, non-violence and control of the senses.

End of quote from book

My extensive research into the origins of the Mevlevi way took many, many years and culminated into the award of a Doctorate. It showed me that there are many misconceptions about Sufism and the Mevlevi in particular. These have naturally come about because 50 or more years of tourism in Konya and that the Mevlevi mainly co-existed in a country which became, over the centuries, more and more fanatically absorbed into the strict Islamic way of life. For many centuries the Mevlevi continued without so much influence from religion. Yet in the two centuries prior to its final demise, Islam was beginning to take over the traditional way. Hence today modern Mevlevi's falsely believe they have to become muslim in order to follow the way of Mevlana. Yet what they do not know is that even in Konya (and most of Turkey) there is a silent majority of more than 60% of the population who do not follow the dictates of Islam. They do not go to the mosque; they do not want to hear the call to prayer disturbing the peace every day. Yet if they speak out they would be condemned by the fanatics. After 43 years of going to stay in Konya I have many friends who are happy to confide in me about these matters. They all agree that the Way of Mevlana was not traditionally a religious way but a way which passes beyond all religions on earth. The Mevlevi Sema is not in any way Islamic.

The Connection with the Study Society in London UK

In London there was a group who followed P.D. Ouspensky's ideas. In the early 19th century PDO visited the Mevlevi Sema in Galata Tekke in Istanbul before it was closed by Attaturk. He made a positive comment about the ceremony in one of his books. The London group use this comment as a way to impress Sheikh Resuhi Baykara to teach the movement of the Sema to a group of their members in London. However, Resuhi had previously been advised by other Sheikhs in Turkey, that Europeans had a very shallow

concept of truly spiritual matters and that they would never really grasp the mystical side of the Mevlevi way; and that they would not likely be able to produce authentic live music for the ceremony, which is vital to the spiritual side of it. The London group were very convincing and Resuhi agreed to give it a try, knowing as he did the difficulties it entailed. For him it was an experiment. After many years and Resuhi's insistence on live music for the ceremony, the London group were unable to learn the music well enough, and continued to use tape recordings.

The many years I spent visiting Istanbul and having teaching from the traditional teachers of the music, impressed Resuhi. I even helped his small group in Istanbul get a better grasp of the music which had been passed to me. However Resuhi had thought that the London group considered him as their Sheikh and they were under his direction. I was a member of the London group at that time and I knew that the decisions of the London group were governed through a European style committee basis. This really meant that decisions about whether or not to continue with the Mevlevi experiment were not made by Resuhi but by the Colet House Committee; this was unknown to Resuhi.

I had become very close to Resuhi over many years and considered him as my Sheikh. He also addressed me as his son; that's how close we were. On one of my many visits to him, he had asked me to instruct the London group about various matters to do with the ceremony and the music. I told him then that it would be difficult to do that, due to the way that decisions were made in London. He was surprised that he did not have the control which he had imagined. On the next visit to Resuhi's home in Istanbul, the following year, he made a profound announcement to me. "I have thought about this for some time and I have decided that I no longer wish to continue as the Sheikh of Colet House. Please will you tell Vilhem Koran this?" I knew how much the people in London cherished their connection with Istanbul and I could not go back to London with such a message. I explained my situation to Resuhi and he accepted it. He then said he would write a letter to Lady Allen (one of the Colet House leaders) and tell her directly his decision. As far as I know, Lady Allen was also unable to tell the whirling group Resuhi's decision, and she simply told them that he had decided to retire. This I knew was not true; hence the fact that Colet House was cut off from the connection with Resuhi was never known by the people there (except Lady Allen). Of course I could also never tell them.

Addendum - by Ud Virtuoso Cinuçen Tanrıkorur

Mevlevi sema in Sutton Surrey UK

"Alan Prosser, is a British disciple of the late Mevlevi Postişin Resuhi Baykara; Alan's eldest daughter Tansy, plays ney. The middle child Andrew plays tanbur, and the younger girl Mary plays kudum. (she is age 21).

"In January 1996 I gave a talk-concert. Then I thought I would mention my oud student Mary Prosser and her family, whom I have known since she was age of 13. The Prossers are received with a little enthusiasm in the UK. Her elder brother Andrew is 23, is a tanburi and whirling dervish, and her elder sister Tansy is 25, is a neyzen and whirling dervish. Their mother plays halile (cymbals). Their house was filled with exquisite (Turkish) calligraphy.

"One Saturday they made sema at which I was present. A large classroom was allocated to them at a Secondary School in Sutton (Surrey UK) for their weekly Mevlevi ritual. There was a polished wooden parquet, which is essential for turning in the sema. An octagonal area, where the sema will be made, is marked with a thin tape on the floor. A plaque brought from their house that reads (in Persian script) "Ya Hazrat Mevlana Celaleddin-i Rumi, kaddesallahu Sirahu" was hung on the wall on the qibla side. (artwork & calligraphy by Alan's wife Anne)

“Alan Prosser is both the naa't-han and a whirling dervish. Together with his two children, Andrew and Tansy, whirled in white tennures and Sikkes on their heads. Mary is both kudumzen and ayinhan, the mother plays halile and they both follow the notes in front of them.

“Alan, after laying down the red sheikh skin (the post) representing Mevlânâ, on the ground in the direction of the qibla, he came to the side of the two-person mutrib (music group) and sang the praise of the Prophet written by Mevlânâ in Persian, with Itri's famous composition in Rast Makam. Then he took his place on the left side of the post as the head of the whirling dervishes. These three whirling dervishes performed the entire Ayin of the great mystic Ahmed Avni Konuk, the great Mevlevi Sufi, in the Makam of Ruy-ı Irak with great dignity and awe, accompanied by two musicians.

Listen at youtube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VssqF84cm6Y&t=3s> (copy and paste into browser)

“The Ayin is over. The last prayers were made. Hirkas, sikkes, neys were collected. The hall was reshaped into a classroom and we left the school. Imagine now. Mevlevi ritual every week at a secondary school in a suburb of London UK. (I was highly delighted) when I saw the harmony in the arms of those children who learned to sing (and make) the whirling from their father, the discipline in their feet, with ablution, and the light of submission on their faces.”

End of quote from Turkish newspaper.

End of Cinuçen's Addendum

Alaeddin Yavasça was also present at that Sema and commented, “I feel I am in Konya!”. Many great Turkish musicians were friends and teachers of the Wenham-Prosser family.

Explanation of the Prison of Religion

In the text of this document I used the expression “the prison of religion”. So that readers do not get a negative impression from this statement, please note the following.

1. Prison is not such a bad place to be. Within it you can be safe from society.
2. You can meet like minded people within prison.
3. There is opportunity for education within prison.
4. You can confront your bad ways of living when in prison.
5. Good resolutions to live a better life can be made within prison.
6. It is possible to get chance to be alone and pray when in prison.
7. All prisons have rules and regulations, which can be a good thing.
8. After release from prison there is the chance to lead a better life.
9. Freedom from prison means you can be yourself as an individual.

These are some of the benefits of prison (religion). But when you have progressed beyond the need to stay there, then the chance of your soul being completely free will not occur until you have escaped (or have been released). Full details in The Bhagavad Gita.

More quotes from the book “The Music of Rumi”

From Chapter Four (on levels of being)

“There are two lines along which man's development proceeds, the line of knowledge and the line of being., people understand what knowledge means. And they understand the possibility of different levels of knowledge. They understand that knowledge may be lesser or greater, that is to say, of one quality or of another quality. But they do not understand this in relation to being,,take for instance the being of a mineral and a plant. It is a different being. The being of a plant and of an animal is again

a different being. The being of an animal and of a man is a different being. But the being of two different people can differ from one another more than the being of a mineral and of an animal. This is exactly what people do not understand."

"And they do not understand that knowledge depends on being. Not only do they not understand this latter but they definitely do not wish to understand it. And especially in Western culture it is considered that a man may possess great knowledge, for example he may be an able scientist, make discoveries, advance science and at the same time he may be, and has the right to be, a petty, egoistic, cavilling, mean, envious, vain, naïve, and absent-minded man., and yet it is his being. And people think that his knowledge does not depend on his being. People of Western culture put great value on the level of a man's knowledge but they do not value the level of a man's being, and are not ashamed of the low-level of their own being. They do not even understand what it means. And they do not understand that the man's knowledge depends on the level of his being."

From P.D. Ouspensky. "In Search of the Miraculous" (London 1964).

From chapter Six (on music and tassavuf)

"A definition of tasawwuf (Sufi mysticism) is a complicated matter, since it is neither a religious sect nor a dogmatic system. It could be described perhaps as a journey or a spiritual pilgrimage where the traveller advances towards communion with God, through slow and difficult stages of asceticism and rigid moral discipline. That spiritual religion of the heart has fully recognised the tremendous spiritual power of music in helping the mind and Soul to concentrate on the idea of God, and in inducing the ecstatic state (wajd) and leading to the passing away from self (fana) which is the ultimate hope and desire of every pledged (Pythagorean) Sufi."

From "The Function of Music in Islamic Culture" -- Dr. El-Kholy.

The Last Word Goes to Mevlana

Above I raised the issue of false Sheikhs. Many will not wish to accept what I say; because they have not realised the difficult (and different) nature of the world we now live in. False religion and false spiritual claims are associated more with raising fame and money than in any recorded time in history; because we live in a world of unprecedented interconnection through the internet and social media etc. etc. Hence the difficulty any true seeker has of finding true guidance in this age is multiplied many times more than in previous centuries. Hence the true seeker is in danger of spending the younger and most productive period of life, wasted on following a false and unproductive trail. This situation is partly the reason I have made this paper available; to warn of this real danger to the true seeker.

With due respect to Mevlana I cannot truly close this paper without giving Him the last word. I consider that He is truly my great²³ grandfather. Therefore as an honest and true grandson I need to show that the phenomenon of false Sheikhs is not a new thing. It clearly was an issue in Mevlana's time. In these modern dark spiritual days a truly holy person would hide their Divinity (though maybe not their advice) from public view, else that person will be "tarred with the same (modern) brush" of fake news and false teachings.

From the Mathnavi of Mevlana (Rumi) Book 1 verses 2264 to 2282

The *header* to the text is Mevlana's prose edit, which are seen throughout the Mathnavi. The form of the original poetry requires exact numbers of syllables per line, hence Mevlana must needs use ellipsis (the omission of obvious words); hence the need for comments. Those within (comment) are those of the translator Reynold A. Nicholson. The comments within [comment] are my own based on the understanding of Mevlana's intentions. Mevlana has left no leaf unturned in this matter, so as to give us all full guidance.

How disciples (novices in Sufism) are beguiled in their need by false imposters and imagine them to be Shaykhs and venerable personages and (saints) united (with God), and

do not know the difference between fact (naqd) and fiction (naql) and between what is tied on (artificially) and what has grown up (naturally). [is truly acquired spiritual guidance]

2264 For this reason the wise have said with knowledge, [of false Shaykhs] 'One must become the guest [be invited] of one who confers benefits.' [knowledge of Truth]

2265 Thou art the disciple and guest of one who, from his vileness [of seeking wealth and fame] robs thee of all thou hast. [takes away your chances of progress]

2266 He is not strong; how should he make thee strong? [to resist fame etc.] He does not give light [of Truth], nay he makes thee dark. [ignorant of Truth].

2267 Since he had no light (in himself), how in association (with him) should others obtain light from him?

2268 (He is) like the half-blind healer of eyes; what should he put in (people's) eyes except jasper? [that which can see nothing]

2269 Such is our state in poverty and affliction; may no guest be beguiled by us! [who are the true teachers]

2270 If thou hast never seen a ten years' famine in (visible) forms, open thine eyes and look at us! [and compare us with the false Shaykhs]

2271 Our outward appearance is like the inward reality of the imposter; [he imitates us in his ways, but really he has] darkness in his heart; his tongue [speech] flashy (plausible).

2272 He has no scent or trace of God, (but) his pretension is greater than (that of) Seth and the and the Father of mankind (Adam).

2273 The Devil [the ignorance of mankind] (is so ashamed of him that he) has not shown to him even his portrait, (yet) he (the imposter) is saying, 'We are of the Abdal [the chief among the saints] and are more (we are superior even to them).

2274 He has stolen many an expression used by [true] dervishes, in order that he himself may be thought to be a (holy) personage.

2275 In his talk he cavils at Bayazid [emperor founder], (although) Yazid [rebellion suppressor] would be ashamed of his existence.

2276 (He is) without (any) portion of the bread and viands [spiritual guidance] of Heaven; God did not throw a single bone to him. [he has failed in his knowledge of Truth]

2277 He has proclaimed, 'I have laid out the dishes, I am the Vicar of God, I am the son of the (spiritual) Khalifa:

2278 Welcome (to the feast), O simple hearted ones, tormented (with hunger) [for Truth], that from my bounteous table ye may eat your fill - of nothing. [i.e. he knows his teaching has no value].

2279 Some persons, (relying) on the promise of 'Tomorrow', [your realisation will come in the future] have wandered for years around that door, (but) 'Tomorrow' never comes.

2280 It needs a long time for the inmost conscience of a man to become evident, [for the true seeker to realise he has been misled], more or less (both in great and small matters),

2281 (So that we may know whether) beneath the wall of his body there is treasure, or whether there is the house of snake and ant and dragon. [the desire for importance, fame and wealth].

2282 When [after all those wasted years] it became clear that he was naught, (worthless), (by that time) the life of the [true] seeker (disciple) had passed: what use (was) the knowledge [of the false trail] (to him)?

Below is the main text without comments so readers can add their own understanding.

2264 For this reason the wise have said with knowledge, 'One must become the guest of one who confers benefits.'

- 2265 Thou art the disciple and guest of one who, from his vileness robs thee of all thou hast.
- 2266 He is not strong; how should he make thee strong? He does not give light, nay he makes thee dark..
- 2267 Since he had no light how in association should others obtain light from him?
- 2268 Like the half-blind healer of eyes; what should he put in eyes except jasper?
- 2269 Such is our state in poverty and affliction; may no guest be beguiled by us!
- 2270 If thou hast never seen a ten years' famine in forms, open thine eyes and look at us!
- 2271 Our outward appearance is like the inward reality of the imposter; darkness in his heart; his tongue flashy.
- 2272 He has no scent or trace of God, his pretension is greater than Seth and the the Father of mankind.
- 2273 The Devil has not shown to him even his portrait, he is saying, 'We are of the Abdal and are more.'
- 2274 He has stolen many an expression used by dervishes, in order that he himself may be thought to be a personage.
- 2275 In his talk he cavils at Bayazid, Yazid would be ashamed of his existence.
- 2276 Without portion of the bread and viands of Heaven; God did not throw a single bone to him.
- 2277 He has proclaimed, 'I have laid out the dishes, I am the Vicar of God, I am the son of the Khalifa:
- 2278 Welcome O simple hearted ones, tormented that from my bounteous table ye may eat your fill - of nothing.
- 2279 Some persons, on the promise of 'Tomorrow', have wandered for years around that door, 'Tomorrow' never comes.
- 2280 It needs a long time for the inmost conscience of a man to become evident, more or less .
- 2281 Beneath the wall of his body there is treasure, or whether there is the house of snake and ant and dragon.
- 2282 When it became clear that he was naught, the life of the seeker had passed: what use the knowledge.

The author and his three children with the Mevlevi Çelebi
The Çelebi Sıtkı Öztürün was a holy man. A direct descendent of Mevlana.

Mevlevi Sema at Çelebi Sıtkı Öztürün's home in Göstepe - Kadıköy - Istanbul

Gönül Sıtkı Alan Andrew

Andrew Sıtkı Gönül

Relaxing at Çelebi Sıtkı Öztürün's home in Göstepe

Tansy Gülsüm Andrew Alan Sıtkı Mary

My son Andrew with Sıtkı

Playing and singing ilahiler at Sıtkı's home

Gülsüm Sıtkı Alan Andrew Gönül

At Nezih Uzel's home Üsküdar

Nezih Tansy Alan

Gülsüm was Sıtkı's sister. Gönül was a Mevlevi family friend.